

Synthesis, characterisation, DNA binding, cleavage and antibacterial studies of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 2,4-dichloro-*N*-((3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-4-yl)methylene)benzohydrazide

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Three mononuclear complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal ions (M) with 2,4-dichloro-*N*-((3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-4-yl)methylene)benzohydrazide (L) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements, molar conductance, IR, ¹H NMR, TGA, UV, LC-MS and ESR spectral studies. The analytical and spectral data suggest that the ligand is tridentate and is coordinating to the metal ions through O, N, O donor atoms. The DNA binding behaviour of the complexes were studied by electronic absorption spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy and viscosity measurements. It was found that the complexes bound to Calf thymus DNA through intercalative mode. The DNA cleavage activity of complexes was studied using of plasmid pBR322 DNA. The antibacterial studies were carried out against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, the results showed the metal complexes to be more active than the ligand.

Keywords: Pyridoxal, DNA binding, fluorescence, viscosity, cleavage studies, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The studies on Schiff bases derived from pyridoxal (3-hydroxy-5-hydroxymethyl-2-methylpyridine-4-carboxaldehyde), a form of vitamin B₆ has been the subject of great interest for many researchers^{1,2}. In the presence of metal ions, free pyridoxal can catalyze a variety of metabolic reactions such as transamination, decarboxylation and racemization of amino acids in which pyridoxal phosphate acts as a co-enzyme¹⁻⁴. Most of the enzymatic reactions could be mimicked by non-enzymatic reactions in which pyridoxal⁵ and metal ions acts as catalyst. Hydrazones are a class of organic compounds in the Schiff base family⁶. The hydrazone Schiff bases of aroyl, acyl and heteroaroyl compounds are known to have an additional donor site, C=O which make them more flexible and versatile⁷. Hydrazone moieties are important due to their diverse pharmacopial activities such as anticancer, antihelminthic, antiviral, antima-

larial, antidepressant and antidiabetic activities⁸⁻¹⁰. Hydrazones also exhibit antituberculosis activity by the formation of stable chelates with the transition metal ions which catalyze physiological processes^{11,12}. The coordination chemistry of pyridoxal semicarbazone (PLSC) based complexes proved to be very interesting as this ligand can exist in neutral, mono and dianionic forms depending on pH. The pyridoxalic fragment is zwitter ion regardless of the form of coordinated ligands: neutral (keto form) and monoanionic (enolic form). Its most predominant tridentate (ONO) coordination mode is achieved through hydrazine nitrogen, phenolic and carbonyl oxygen atoms allows it to be excellent chelating agent¹³.

One of the major health concerns of human society is cancer, which is the primary target of medicinal chemists. Platinum based complexes¹⁴ have been efficient anticancer chemotherapy agents. But they possesses inherent limitations as side effects and ac-

quired drug resistance^{15,16}. In order to find different metal complexes with better anticancer activity with less side effects, there is a shift in interest to develop non-platinum complexes¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Based on the cytotoxicity activities of some copper(II) complexes²⁰⁻²², they may also be considered for anticancer studies. The *in vitro* anticancer studies on MCF-7 human breast cancer cells using some Ni^{II} complexes also found to inhibit cell proliferation²³. DNA being the storage and carrier molecule of genetic information, it is a major target for drug interaction due to the ability of DNA-bound drugs to interfere with transcription and replication in the cell. Interaction of DNA with small molecules can cause damage in cancer cells by blocking the division and resulting in the destruction of cancer cell^{24,25}. The studies on the interaction of transition metal complexes with DNA are of importance in design and development of chemotherapeutic drugs^{26,27}. In view of the enormous pharmacological potential of the ligand based on pyridoxal moiety and hydrazone, we report the synthesis, characterisation, DNA binding, cleavage and antibacterial studies of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff base ligand (L) 2,4-dichloro-*N*-(3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-4-yl)methylene)benzohydrazide derived from pyridoxal and 2,4-

dichloro benzohydrazide. The ligand (L) exhibits keto-enol tautomerism (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

The Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal ion (M) complexes of 2,4-dichloro-*N*-(3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-4-yl)methylene)benzohydrazide (L) were obtained as solids. The complexes are coloured, amorphous, stable in air and soluble in DMSO and DMF and insoluble in most of the organic solvents and water.

Elemental analysis, molar conductivity and magnetic moment measurements:

The elemental analysis and physical properties data of the ligand (L) and its metal complexes, **1-3** are presented in the Table 1. The results are in good agreement with the calculated values. The data obtained indicate the formation of (1:2) complexes, ML₂ wherein the ligand coordinated in a tridentate fashion through O,N,O donor atoms i.e. oxygen atom of phenolic OH, nitrogen atom of azomethine and oxygen atom of carbonyl group. The molar conductivities of 10⁻³ M solutions of each complex in DMSO were measured at room temperature. The molar conductance values (Table 1) are in the range of 5–10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, which are low. These values sug-

Fig. 1. Keto-enol tautomerism of ligand.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of ligand and its metal complexes **1-3**

Compound	Empirical formula	Colour	Analysis (%): Found (Calcd.)			Conductivity (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Yield (%)
			C	H	N			
L	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂	Pale yellow	50.61 (50.84)	3.54 (3.67)	11.73 (11.86)	5	–	79.25
1 Ni(L) ₂	NiC ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₄	Brick red	47.12 (47.07)	3.09 (3.14)	10.82 (10.98)	10	2.875	68.03
2 Cu(L) ₂	CuC ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₄	Dark green	46.32 (46.75)	3.14 (3.11)	10.85 (10.91)	6	1.792	64.71
3 Zn(L) ₂	ZnC ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₄	Yellow	46.03 (46.63)	3.17 (3.10)	10.79 (10.88)	9	Diamagnetic	62.00

gest that the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. Magnetic moment, μ_{eff} values of the complexes **1** and **2** are 2.87 and 1.79 B.M. respectively, suggest the presence of two unpaired electrons in Ni^{II} and one unpaired electron in Cu^{II} complex with paramagnetic nature. The magnetic moment, μ_{eff} value of the Zn^{II} complex is zero indicate its diamagnetic nature.

Liquid chromatography-mass spectra (LCMS):

The liquid chromatogram of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes showed single peak with retention time at 0.214, 0.752 and 0.670 min indicating purity of the respective complexes.

Mass spectrum of the ligand (L) showed peak with m/z value at 353.8 [M]⁺ which corresponds to [C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₃Cl₂]⁺ molecular ion. Peaks at m/z 356 [M+2]⁺ and m/z 358 [M+4]⁺ along with [M]⁺ in the ratio of 9:6:1 were also observed due to the presence of two chlorine atoms in the ligand. These peaks in the molecular ion region arise due to various combinations of chlorine isotopes (³⁵Cl and ³⁷Cl). The mass spectra of Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ (**1-3**) complexes showed molecular ion peak [M]^{+•} at m/z 764, 770 and 774 respectively, confirming the stoichiometry of the metal to ligand ratio to be 1:2 (ML₂) in all complex systems. The mass spectrum of Ni(L)₂ complex showed peak at m/z 414 was attributed to (NiL)^{+•} fragment ion, peak at m/z 353 corresponds to (C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₃Cl₂)^{+•} ligand species peak at m/z 190 and 147 were due to (C₆H₄-Cl₂-CONH)^{+•} and (C₆H₄-Cl₂)^{+•} fragment ions. The mass spectrum of Zn(L)₂ complex showed a peak at m/z 790 corresponds to (ZnL₂H₂O)^{+•}. Along with the [M]⁺ molecular ion peak, [M+2] and [M+4] peaks were also observed in all the complexes in the ratio of 9:6:1.

IR spectra:

In order to understand the binding mode of the

ligand to the metal in the complexes, the IR spectral data of the ligand and metal complexes are presented in the Table 2. The absorption band corresponding to phenolic-OH group $\nu(\text{O-H})$ at 3429 cm⁻¹ was absent in all complexes suggesting coordination through phenolic oxygen. This is further supported by a shift in band at 1278 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(\text{C-O})_{\text{phenolic}}$ stretching by 20–40 cm⁻¹ ²⁸⁻³⁰ in the complexes due to coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal ion. The IR spectrum of the ligand showed strong band at 1641 cm⁻¹ due to azomethine group $\nu(\text{C=N})$, which is shifted to lower frequency indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen in all the complexes. The band observed at 1701 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of the carbonyl group $\nu(\text{C=O})$ in the ligand, which is shifted to 1674 cm⁻¹ in the Ni^{II} complex indicating coordination through carbonyl oxygen in the keto (neutral) form. The disappearance of band corresponding to carbonyl group $\nu(\text{C=O})$ in the IR spectra of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes suggests enolisation (monoanionic) form. This is supported by formation of new peaks which corresponds to $\nu(\text{C-O})_{\text{enolic}}$ at 1195 cm⁻¹, 1199 cm⁻¹ for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes and $\nu(\text{C=N})$ at 1587 cm⁻¹ for both the complexes suggesting coordination through enolic oxygen. In the metal complexes, Schiff base assumes the zwitter ionic form due to the migration of phenolic hydrogen atom to pyridine nitrogen. The appearance of one or more bands in the range of 2800–2950 cm⁻¹ corresponds to $\nu(\text{NH}^+)$ vibrations indicating the dipolar nature of pyridoxal moiety^{31,32}. This band is present in Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, but absent in Ni^{II} complex, indicating deprotonation. The appearance of new bands in the regions 500–550 cm⁻¹ and 400–450 cm⁻¹ is due to M-O and M-N bonds respectively. The IR spectral analysis suggest that the ligand acts as a tridentate O,N,O donor and is coordinating through phenolic oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen to the metal ion.

Table 2. Characteristic IR bands (cm⁻¹) of the ligand and its complexes

Compound	$\nu(\text{O-H})$	$\nu(\text{N-H})$	$\nu(\text{NH}^+)$	$\nu(\text{C=O})$	$\nu(\text{C=N})$	$\nu(\text{C-O})_{\text{enolic}}$
L	3429	3190	2850	1701	1641	–
1 Ni(L) ₂	–	3170	–	1674	1631	–
2 Cu(L) ₂	–	–	2867	–	1610, 1587	1195
3 Zn(L) ₂	–	–	2856	–	1610, 1587	1199

Thermogravimetric analysis:

The thermograms of the Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ complexes suggest the decomposition pattern of all the complexes to be similar. The thermogram of Ni(L)₂ complex (Fig. 4.3.9) shows decomposition of complex moiety in two steps as curves between 280–700°C. The residue left (11.1%) which can be due to metal oxide (NiO). The thermogram Cu(L)₂ complex (Fig. 4.3.10) was stable upto 300°C indicates the absence of water molecules. At 300°C there was sudden weight loss of 44.9% and from then there was slow decomposition of complex moiety. The residue left is 12.3% which can be attributed to copper oxide. The Zn(L)₂ complex (Fig. 4.3.11) showed a weight loss of 2.84% between 100–300°C which indicates presence of one lattice water molecule. The complex is stable upto 300°C and thereafter undergoes slow decomposition of the complex moiety between 300–800°C. The residue left is 12.81% which corresponds to zinc oxide.

¹H NMR spectra:

A comparison ¹H NMR spectrum of ligand with Zn(L)₂ complex gives an evidence for complexation of the ligand. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the Zn(L)₂ complex, the -OH peak at δ 12.68 ppm (1H, s) assigned to phenolic proton attached to the pyridine ring is absent, indicating coordination through oxygen. The signal at 12.02 ppm (1H, s) of amide proton (-CO-NH-) has disappeared due to conversion of keto to enol form and coordination through enolic oxygen atom in the complex. Shift of azomethine proton from 8.80 ppm (1H, s) to 8.89 ppm (1H, s) in the complex indicate the participation of azomethine nitrogen in coordination to Zn^{II} metal ion.

EPR spectrum:

The EPR spectrum of the Cu(L)₂ complex was recorded at room temperature. The spectrum showed three 'g' values, 2.228, 2.091 and 1.982 corresponding to g_x, g_y and g_z respectively, due to anisotropy. This suggests distorted octahedral geometry for the Cu(L)₂ complex³⁴.

Electronic spectra:

The electronic spectrum of the ligand showed intense peak at 34362 cm⁻¹ and 29542 cm⁻¹ which

corresponds to π-π* and n-π* transitions of the pyridoxal moiety and imine group. The UV-Visible spectrum of Ni(L)₂ complex showed d-d transitions at 11614 cm⁻¹, 16474 cm⁻¹ and 26881 cm⁻¹ due to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) respectively, indicating an octahedral geometry for the complex. The band at 37878 cm⁻¹ was due to CT transition. The Cu(L)₂ complex showed in the electronic spectrum transitions at 10867 cm⁻¹, 15037 cm⁻¹ and 21630 cm⁻¹ due to ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_{1g} respectively, indicating a distorted octahedral geometry for the complex. The band at 37037 cm⁻¹ belongs to CT transition³³.

Probable geometry of the complexes:

Based on elemental analysis, spectral and magnetic moment data the probable geometry and tentative structure for the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are given (Fig. 2).

*DNA binding studies:**Electronic absorption titration:*

Absorption spectroscopy is widely used to study the binding strength and binding mode of DNA with the metal complex. The extent of binding strength of the metal complex to the DNA is quantitatively determined by calculating its intrinsic binding constant (K_b). Transition metal complexes can bind to DNA through covalent and non-covalent interactions. In covalent binding, the labile ligand of the complex can be replaced by a nitrogen base of DNA such as guanine (N7) and the non-covalent interactions include intercalative, groove and electrostatic binding³⁴. In case of intercalative binding mode of complex to DNA, hypochromism with significant bathochromic (red) shift or hypsochromic (blue) shift is observed due to strong π-π interaction between the DNA base pairs and the aromatic chromophore of the ligand. The extent of hypochromism suggests the strength of intercalation³⁵. The absorption titration experiments of Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ complexes in Tris-HCl buffer solution (pH 7.2) were performed by using different concentrations of CT DNA (10–100 μL), keeping the concentration of the complex to be constant. After the addition of DNA to the metal complex, the resulting solution was allowed to equilibrate.

Fig. 2. Tentative structures of the complexes [Ni(L)₂] (1), [Cu(L)₂] (2) and [Zn(L)₂] (3).

brate for 10 min before recording each spectrum. The binding constant, K_b of the complexes were determined using the eq. (1). The plots $[DNA]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ versus $[DNA]$ gave a slope equal to $1/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ and the intercept equal to $1/K_b (\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$. The K_b is given by the ratio of slope and intercept. The DNA binding studies suggests that the Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and

Zn(L)₂ complexes show hypochromic shift and bathochromic shift indicating intercalative mode of binding. Intercalation involves insertion of a planar molecule between DNA base pairs, which results in the decrease in the DNA helical twist and lengthening of DNA³⁶. The binding constant (K_b) of the Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ complexes (Fig. 3), were found to be 0.7675×10^4 , 1.0741×10^4 and $0.5616 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ respectively.

Competitive DNA binding fluorescence studies:

Ethidium bromide (3,8-diamino-5-ethyl-6-phenylanthridium bromide) (EB) is used as a probe due to its high fluorescence intensity when bound to the nucleic acid. The competitive DNA binding of complexes has been studied by monitoring the changes in the emission intensity of EB bound to CT-DNA when a metal complex is added. In the presence of CT-DNA, EB emits intense fluorescence at about 580–600 nm due to its tenable intercalation between the adjacent DNA base pairs. The metal complex shows affinity towards DNA, which may result in quenching of the emission intensity of EB bound to CT-DNA. The extent of fluorescence quenching of EB bound to CT-DNA can be attributed to competitive binding of the metal complex to CT-DNA displacing EB or changes in the secondary structure of DNA. The emission spectra of EB bound to DNA in the absence and presence of metal complexes are shown in the Fig. 4. The addition of Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ complexes (1-3) to DNA pretreated with EB results in quenching of emission intensity, indicating the displacement of EB from the EB-DNA adduct. As the metal complexes 1-3 have planar ligands, they replace EB from intercalative binding sites due to which quenching of emission intensity of DNA-EB is observed. The quenching plots of I_0/I versus r (insets of Fig. 4) are in good agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation. The K_{sv} values were calculated to be 0.440, 0.721 and 0.202 M^{-1} respectively for the complexes 1-3.

Viscosity measurements:

Viscosity measurements were carried out to ascertain the nature of binding of the metal complexes with CT-DNA. A classical intercalation model sug-

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of the complexes 1-3 (20 μ M) in absence (black) and in presence (colours) of increasing amounts of CT-DNA, [DNA] = 10–100 μ M. Arrow indicates hypochromism with increase in concentration of DNA. Linear plots for the calculation of intrinsic binding constant.

Fig. 4. Emission spectra of EB bound to CT-DNA in the absence (–) and in presence (colours) of complexes 1-3 (50 μ M). Inset: Stern-Volmer quenching curve. Arrow indicates quenching with increase in concentration of complex.

gests that the DNA double helix must lengthen as base pairs are separated to accommodate the binding molecule, which leads to increase in the viscosity of DNA. EB is a potential intercalator which shows a significant increase in viscosity by lengthening the DNA helix through intercalation. When the concentration of the complexes **1-3** was increased, they showed increase in relative viscosity similar to EB, indicating insertion of the ligand between the base pairs of DNA. The resultant data is presented as plot of $(\eta'_{sp}/\eta_{sp})^{1/3}$ versus r . The order of viscosity is EB > Cu(L)₂ > Ni(L)₂ > Zn(L)₂ as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Effect of increasing amounts of the EB, Cu(L)₂, Ni(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ complexes on the relative viscosities of CT-DNA at 25°C.

DNA cleavage studies:

In order to evaluate the DNA cleavage ability of the complexes **1-3**, super coiled (SC) plasmid pBR322 DNA (100 ng/μL) was incubated with varying concentrations of complexes (20–60 μM) in DMSO, in Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2) for 1 h at 37°C and gel electrophoresis study was carried out. Migration of

plasmid DNA occurs under the influence of electric potential and it depends on the DNA size, electric field and buffer density. Since DNA is a charged species under electric field, it migrates towards anode. When circular plasmid DNA was subjected to electrophoresis, the intact super coiled DNA migrates relatively fast. If scission occurs on one strand, the super coiled form will relax to generate slow moving nicked circular form. If both the strands are cleaved, a linear form will be generated that migrates between super coiled form and nicked circular form. Hydrolytic cleavage agents cleave nucleic acids through phosphodiester bond hydrolysis mechanism³⁸. It was observed that Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ metal complexes (**1-3**) are able to cleave DNA without any added reagents or light and as they contain nucleophiles such as hydroxyl groups in the ligand, indicating the hydrolytic cleavage of DNA. It is evident from the Fig. 6, that all the complexes were able to convert DNA, its super coiled form (SC) to nicked circular form (NC) suggesting that the complexes have nicking activity and with increase in concentration of the metal complexes the cleavage activity also increased.

Fig. 6. Agarose gel electrophoresis pattern for the cleavage of supercoiled pBR322 DNA by complexes **1-3**. Lane 0 DNA control, Lane 1-3 DNA + **1** (20, 40, 60 μM), Lane 4-6 DNA + **2** (20, 40, 60 μM), Lane 7-9 DNA + **3** (20, 40, 60 μM).

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of ligand and its metal complexes (mm)

Compound	Conc. (μg/mL)	Gram-negative bacteria				Gram-positive bacteria	
		Zone of inhibition (mm)					
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	DMSO	
L	500	25	21	23	22		
1 Ni(L) ₂	500	29	32	27	25		
2 Cu(L) ₂	500	32	35	30	29		
3 Zn(L) ₂	500	28	21	26	22		
Ampicillin	500	36	39	34	35		

Antibacterial activity:

The ligand (L) and its metal complexes **1-3** were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus* and the results are presented in the Table 3. All complexes showed good antibacterial activity than the ligand. The enhanced activity of the metal complexes can be due to their greater permeability into bacterial cell membrane which facilitates better antibacterial activity³⁹. The Cu(L)₂ complex showed better activity than other complexes.

Experimental

Materials and chemicals:

Solvents and chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and used without further purification. Pyridoxal hydrochloride and Calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Metal chlorides of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were procured from SD fine chemicals. pBR322 DNA was obtained from Sisco Research Laboratories. Tris-HCl, tris-base, ethidium bromide and agarose were procured from Himedia.

Synthesis of ligand:

We have recently reported the synthesis and characterisation of pyridoxal (Vitamin B₆) derivatives, derived from the condensation of pyridoxal with substituted benzohydrazides⁴⁰.

2,4-Dichloro-N'-((3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-4-yl)methylene) benzohydrazide: Analytical data: yellow solid; yield: 78%; m.p. 220°C; IR (KBr): ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) ν (O-H) 3429, ν (N-H) 3190, ν (NH⁺) 2850, ν (C=O) 1701, ν (C=N) 1641, ν (C-O)_{phenolic} 1278; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆ δ /ppm): δ 12.68 (1H, s), 12.02 (9.92, 1H, s), 8.80 (8.61, 1H, s), 7.96 (7.93, 1H, s), 7.82 (1H, d, *J* 10.8 Hz), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 10.8 Hz), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz), 5.93 (5.29, 1H, brs), 4.58 (4.50, 2H, brs), 2.42 (2.25, 3H, s); ¹³C NMR (270 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆ δ /ppm): δ 162, 152, 151, 144, 143, 140, 136, 133, 130, 129, 129, 127, 126, 58.2, 14.8. ESI- MS: *m/z* 353.8 [M]⁺.

Synthesis of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes (1-3):

To a solution of ligand (4 mmol) dissolved in 20 mL ethanol, metal(II) chlorides (2 mmol) dissolved in ethanol was added. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h. The pH was adjusted to 8, by addition of few drops of ethanolic ammonia. The precipitate formed was filtered and washed with ethanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ under vacuum.

Physical measurements:

An elemental analysis of CHN was performed using Thermo Finnigan 1112 elemental analyzer. Melting points were recorded on a Toshniwal hot stage apparatus in open capillary tubes. LC-MS of ligand and its complexes were recorded on Shimadzu LCMS-2010A spectrometer. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu Prestige-21 FTIR spectrometer in KBr disc. UV spectra were recorded in DMSO solution on Shimadzu UV 2450 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker WH (270 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard with chemical shift, δ ppm. Thermogravimetric (TG) analyses were performed using Shimadzu TGA-50H in nitrogen atmosphere in the temperature range of 0°C to 1000°C with a ramp of 20°C per min. Magnetic moment measurements were carried out on Gouy balance (Model 7550) using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as standard. ESR spectrum of Cu^{II} complex was recorded on Jeol Model JES-FA200 ESR spectrometer with X and Q band. DNA binding studies were carried out by recording absorption spectra using Shimadzu UV 2450 spectrophotometer. Emission spectral study was carried out by using Shimadzu RF 5301 PC spectrofluorophotometer and viscosity measurements were carried out using an Ostwalds viscometer maintained at a constant temperature of 30.0±0.1°C in a thermostatic waterbath. Antimicrobial activity was tested using Agar well diffusion method.

DNA binding and cleavage studies:

Methodology of DNA binding using electronic absorption titration:

All the experiments involving interaction of DNA with the metal complexes were carried out in Tris-HCl buffer (50 mM, pH 7.2). Calf thymus DNA

(CT-DNA) was purified by centrifugation before use. A solution of CT-DNA in the buffer gave a ratio of UV absorbance (A) at 260 and 280 nm (A_{260}/A_{280}) 1.8–1.9 indicating that the DNA was sufficiently free from protein contamination³⁹. The concentration of DNA was determined by measuring the UV absorbance at 260 nm using $\epsilon = 6600 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$. The stock solution was stored at 4°C and used within 2 days. Spectroscopic titrations were performed by maintaining the metal complex concentration to be constant while varying the CT-DNA concentration. The absorption due to free CT-DNA was eliminated by adding an equimolar amount of CT-DNA to both the complex solution and the reference solution. After the addition of DNA to the metal complex, the resulting solution was allowed to equilibrate for 10 min, after which absorption spectrum was recorded. The resulting spectrum was considered to result from the interaction of metal complex with DNA. From the absorption data, the intrinsic binding constant (K_b) was determined by plotting $[\text{DNA}]/[\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f]$ versus $[\text{DNA}]$ according to the eq. (1).

$$\frac{[\text{DNA}]}{[\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f]} = \frac{[\text{DNA}]}{[\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f]} + \frac{1}{K_b} [\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f] \quad (1)$$

where, $[\text{DNA}]$ is the concentration of DNA in base pairs, ϵ_a , ϵ_f and ϵ_b are apparent, unbound (free) and fully bound complex absorption coefficients respectively. A plot of $[\text{DNA}]/[\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f]$ versus $[\text{DNA}]$ gave a slope $1/[\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f]$ and y-intercept equal to $(1/K_b)[\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f]$ respectively. The intrinsic binding constant K_b is the ratio of the slope to intercept.

Competitive DNA binding fluorescence studies:

Fluorescence spectroscopic method was used to study the relative binding of the complexes to CT-DNA, by the displacement of ethidium bromide (EB) bound to CT-DNA in a Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2).

The quenching of the EB-DNA adduct fluorescence is studied by following the emission spectra of the complex in the wavelength range of 530–720 nm with an excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}) of 520 nm, upon addition of different concentrations of metal complex to DNA pretreated with EB.

The fluorescence quenching was determined by

using the Stern-Volmer (eq. (2)).

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv} r \quad (2)$$

where, I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities of the DNA-EB adduct in absence and in presence of the complex respectively. K_{sv} is the Stern-Volmer quenching constant and ' r ' is the ratio of the concentration of the complex to that of DNA. The K_{sv} value is given by the ratio of slope to intercept in a plot of I_0/I vs $[\text{complex}]/[\text{DNA}]$ or ' r ', which indicate the extent of binding of complex to CT-DNA. The concentrations of each EB and DNA solutions taken were 20 μM and that of complex was 50 μM .

Viscosity measurements:

Viscosity measurements were carried out using Ostwald viscometer maintained at $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ in a thermostat. Titrations were performed for the metal complexes (50 μM) which were introduced into CT-DNA solution (200 μM) in Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2) present in the viscometer. Flow times were recorded for different concentrations of complex by maintaining the concentration of CT-DNA to be constant (200 μM). The solution was mixed thoroughly and average values of three measurements were taken to determine the viscosity of the complexes. The resultant data were presented as $(\eta'_{\text{sp}}/\eta_{\text{sp}})^{1/3}$ versus r , where r is the ratio of the concentration of the complex to that of DNA, η'_{sp} is the viscosity of DNA in the presence of the complex and η_{sp} is the viscosity of DNA alone. The concentration of DNA and EB taken were 200 μM and 50 μM respectively.

DNA cleavage studies:

The cleavage of supercoiled pBR322 DNA was monitored by Agarose gel electrophoresis technique. The samples were incubated for 2 h at 37°C containing plasmid DNA (300 ng/3 μL), metal complexes in DMSO (20–60 μM) and Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2). The gel electrophoresis experiment was performed by loading the samples onto a 1% agarose gel containing EB (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) after mixing 1 μL of loading buffer (1% bromophenol blue and 40% sucrose). The gel was run in TAE buffer pH 8.0 (40 mM Tris-base, 20 mM acetic acid and 1 mM EDTA) at a constant voltage, until the bromophenol blue had traveled through 75% of the gel. The bands were visualized.

lized by viewing the gel under a transilluminator and photographed.

Antibacterial activity:

The antibacterial activity was evaluated by well diffusion method in nutrient agar medium. The required concentration of the compounds were prepared in sterile DMSO. The molten Mueller Hinton Agar was poured into the Petri plate and allowed to solidify. Wells were prepared in the plates with the help of a cork-borer (0.85 cm). The bacterial suspension was swabbed on agar bed using a sterile cotton swab, followed by introducing 100 μ L of the complex solution into the well. The plates were then incubated for 24 h at 37°C. The compounds were evaluated for antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus*. An antibiotic, Ampicillin (500 μ g/mL) was used as standard reference. Dimethyl sulphoxide was used as control. The antibacterial potency was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm.

Conclusion

The elemental analysis, spectral and magnetic moment data indicated that the ligand is tridentate, coordinated through O, N, O donor atoms and forms chelates with the metal ions. Octahedral geometry was proposed for all complexes. Absorption spectra, fluorescence spectra and viscosity measurements suggest that all the complexes interact with CT-DNA by intercalative mode through nitrogenous bases of DNA. The binding constant K_b of the Ni(L)₂, Cu(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ metal complexes were found to be 0.7675×10^4 , 1.0741×10^4 and 0.5616×10^4 M⁻¹ respectively. The Cu(L)₂ showed better DNA binding ability than Ni(L)₂ and Zn(L)₂ complexes, which are consistent with the quenching studies and viscosity measurements. All the complexes are able to cleave plasmid pBR322 DNA and convert DNA from super coiled form to nicked circular form, suggesting that the complexes have nicking activity. The antibacterial activity studies found the metal complexes to exhibit better activity than free ligand.

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Kavitha R. *et al.*: Synthesis, characterisation, DNA binding, cleavage and antibacterial studies *etc.*

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